

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF GRADUONYMY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Avezova Rakhila

Master student at the department of English language and literature Urgench State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7314415>

Abstract. This article provides information about the graduonymy in English and Uzbek languages, particularly, their stylistic features. Furthermore, it is explained that words in a graduonymic row can be graded not only by a single meaning, but also by a number of interrelated meanings and stylistic colors.

Keywords: graduonymy, stylistic features, synonymy, language change, concepts, denotative meaning, connotative meaning.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГРАДУОНИМИИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В статье представлены сведения о градуонимии в английском и узбекском языках, в частности, их стилистических особенностях. Кроме того, поясняется, что слова в градуонимическом ряду могут быть классифицированы не только по одному значению, но и по ряду взаимосвязанных значений и стилистических окрасок.

Ключевые слова: градуонимия, стилистические признаки, синонимия, изменение языка, концепты, денотативное значение, коннотативное значение.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a constantly moving, dynamic phenomenon, the units of which are constantly changing as a result of various external and internal factors. The nature of language, its origins, the attitudes of communicators towards language, as well as the influence of other languages and cultures on language, give rise to different characteristics and spiritual relationships in language. To date, most of these relationships have been studied by local and global scholars, but some specific aspects are still awaiting their study.

One such lexical phenomenon is the semantic relationship between words. Although antonyms, synonyms, and homonyms have been sufficiently studied in the semantic relations between words, in recent years a great deal of scientific work has been done to study the phenomenon of graduonymy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dividing words into specific groups to represent different levels of character traits is not entirely new to linguistics, and their notation as coincidences has a long history in linguistics. In Uzbek linguistics, for example, we find Alisher Navoi's "Muhokama-tul-lug'atayn", in which, Navoi distinguishes the following series of hierarchies, which represent the state of "laughing":

iljaymoq~jilmaymoq~kulimsiramog~tirjaymoq~xoxolab kulmoq[5]. It seems that the subject of the art of using graded words in the works of Alisher Navoi can be a source of several studies.

The division of the Uzbek language vocabulary into lexical groups is closely related to the study of inter-verbal semantics. Until the mid-1980s, Uzbek linguistics understood the concept of inter-word semantic relations mainly as two types of synonyms and antonyms.

The work of Uzbek linguist R. Safarova raises the issue that the types of semantic relations between words are not limited to these semantic relations, and one aspect of the new modern relations is the analysis of gender relations in the example of animal names.

R.Safarova and E.Begmatov, H.Nematov, R.Rasulov, who are the authors of “Lexical microsystem and its research methods” in order to show that they could have rhymes, they mentioned graduonimic (hierarchy), partonimic (whole-part), functionality (functionality) relations. It has long been known in linguistics that lexical units form a series of hierarchies according to their semantic relations.

In today's linguistics, the terms graduonymy and its Uzbek meaning of hierarchy are gaining popularity as a scientific concept that refers to a form of inter-verbal semantic relations.

Sh. Orifjonova has also worked on the graduonomic series of grading in the Uzbek language. Orifjonova's dissertation is a summary of the information provided by other linguists on this topic. A. Hodjiev also dwells on the gradients and expresses his valuable comments. About graduonomic series of rhymes U. Tursunov, J. Mukhtorov Sh. Rakhmatullayev also spoke and concluded: “Demonstrative pronouns are used depending on the distance between the speaker and the object, the time of the incident. This pronoun is used to emphasize a well-known, recently mentioned object, event, or object in general.” From ancient times to the present day, the work of our linguists has been a valuable resource. As we read them, we are once again convinced that there are many aspects of the graduonomic series that have not yet been touched, and that they are still awaiting their solution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, we aimed to study the stylistic features of the phenomenon of graduonymy in English and Uzbek, as well as using methods such as comparative method, descriptive method, distributive analysis method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The term “graduonymy” belongs to the Greek language and means “Gradatio - rise, growth” and “onymo – name”. It has long been known to science that lexical units form a series of hierarchies according to their spiritual relationship, and the most striking example of this is the series of words containing the word “o’rta” (middle). For example: *katta – o’rta – kichik yosh – o’rta – qari uzoq – o’rta – yaqin baland – o’rta – past uzun – o’rta – qisqa*. It is known that the sign-property, expressed by the word middle, literally means the state between the middle, that is, between two opposing signs. When the lexeme “o’rta” is in the range of antonyms, *katta – o’rta – kichik graduonymy* is less noticeable. However, if the lexeme “o’rta” are perceived not on the basis of the opposite sign, but on the basis of the decrease or increase of a certain sign, the semantic graduonymy is clearly understood.

Words in a graduonymic row can be graded not only by a single semantics, but also by a number of interrelated semantics and stylistic colors.

The essence of the non-linguistic factor is that there is a difference in quality as well as a difference in quantity. For example, a person experiences the period of infancy, youth, adolescence, maturity, old age, and plant witnesses germination, seedlings, maturity, and drought - growth. The colors and other characteristics of nature are so diverse that painters can distinguish even more than a dozen types of black. The active consciousness of man reflects this quantitative and qualitative difference. Since language is an expression of consciousness, it must also express the same quantitative differences reflected in consciousness. Such quantitative

differences are represented in a variety of ways, including by individual lexemes. For example, urug' - kurtak - meva; *ninni* – *chaqaloq*, *bo'taloq* - *tuya* , *buzoq* – *tana* – *g'unajin* – *sigir* .

The linguistic factor for distinguishing a graduonymic lexical line is:

- a) the semantic factor;
- b) paradigmatic relationship between words.

The essence of the semantic factor in the separation of the graduonymic line is that in the semantics of a number of lexemes there is a reference to the degree of a certain sign, to different degrees. For example, let's look at the explanation of the window-door-gate lexeme in the Uzbek

Explanatory Dictionary:

1. A window is a small door with one or two panes, a door, or a wall that once served as a window.

2. A door is an opening and closing device installed at the entrance of a house, room, building or yard.

3. A gate is a large door that opens and closes into a courtyard, a fortress, a castle, a factory, etc.

This description is definitely not perfect. Because they are described separately from their gradient system. If they were analyzed as members of the same system, they would have the following characteristics:

1. **Gulobi** - a pink color, ranging from white to red and pink.
2. **Pushti** - peach blossom, bright red, darker than pink.
3. **Qizg'ish** - darker than pink, brighter than red, reddish.
4. **Qizil**- the color of blood.
5. **Ol** - a darker color than red.
6. **Qirmizi**- dark red.

Thus, the semantic factor for the separation of the lexical graduonomic line is manifested in the fact that in each lexeme among the representatives of the closely related concept there is a reference to the different degrees of a particular sign. On this basis, the semantic factor itself can be divided into two types:

- 1) express similar concepts;
- 2) referring to different amounts of the same symbol.

The graduonymic series meets all of the following requirements for a lexical paradigm:

- 1) the unification of a lexical paradigm around a single leading lexeme (dominant);
- 2) openness of the lexical paradigm;
- 3) the lexical paradigm becomes part of another larger paradigm as the leading lexeme;
- 4) the surrounding lexeme in the lexical paradigm can be easily replaced by the dominant lexeme.

Thus, the phenomenon of graduonymy, which is a linguistic relationship between lexemes, is the manifestation of several lexemes in a system of lexical semantics, depending on the number of specific characters, in which the dominant and surrounding lexemes are distinguished.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we must define that the lexical graduonomic series contains the most general laws of dialectics:

a) the law of the transition of quantitative change to qualitative change in the graduation, increase or expansion of the sign in the graduonomic line is developed;

b) the mutually contradictory (antonymous relationship) lexemes unite around one dominant lexeme (dominant) and form a lexical-spiritual line - the paradigm, the unity of opposition and the law of struggle in the formation of wholeness.

REFERENCES

1. Begmatov E. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tilining leksik qatlamlari.- Toshkent: fan, 1985.-200b
2. Bozorov O. Lisoniy darajalanuvchi o'rganish asoslari// Muosir Buxoro filologiyasi. Buxoro, 1994. –I juz. –B. 35-38
3. Jumaniyozov P. Sinonimlar tarifi masalasi// o'zbek tili va adabiyoti.-1970. 41-42b
4. . Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида лексик градуонимия. Монография. –Тошкент. Мумтоз сўз, 2014. 9 б.т.
5. Orifjonova Sh, “O'zbek tilida lug'aviy graduonimiya” f.f.n. dess. avtoreferat. Toshkent, 1997. 16-bet
6. Djumabaeva J.Sh. Graduonymy as a semantic phenomenon in Uzbek linguistics// Arts and Social Sciences Journal (ISSN: 2151-6200) OMICS International Journals. Volume 7, №4. 2016. Journal Impact Factor 0.118; 1.23 (5 Year Impact Factor)
7. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Лисоний даражаланиш тадқиқи хусусида. //Илм сарчашмалари (УрганчДУ), 2009. № 4. –Б. 79-80. (10.00.00; №3)
8. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Лексик системада градуонимик муносабатлар ва инглиз тили лексикаси градуонимик қаторлари хусусида. //Филология масалалари. (ЎзДЖТУ), 2009 №3-4 (24). –Б. 57-61. (10.00.00; №18)
9. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Некоторые взгляды на миронимию английских лингвистов. // БухДУ илмий ахбороти, 2010. №2. –Б. 57-60. (10.00.00; №1)
10. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Ранг-тус билдирувчи сифатларнинг контекстуал антонимлари ва уларнинг инглиз тилидан ўзбек тилига таржимаси хусусида. //Хорижий филология. Тил. Адабиёт. Таълим. (СамДЧТИ), 2010. №1(34). –Б. 15-17. (10.00.00; №10)
11. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Градуонимия ва бошқа семантик категориялар хусусида. //ЎзМУ хабарлари. 2010. №1. –Б. 53-55. (10.00.00; №15)
12. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида феъллар градуонимияси.// ЎзМУ хабарлари. 2012. №1. –Б. 232-235. (10.00.00; №15)
13. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Градуаллик ва градуонимия.// Илм сарчашмалари (УрганчДУ), 2012. №2. –Б. 41-43. (10.00.00; №3)
14. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Инглиз тилида олмош ва равиш градуонимияси.// ЎзМУ хабарлари. 2013. Махсус сон. –Б. 193-196. (10.00.00; №15)
15. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Градуонимия ва синонимия.// Хорижий филология. Тил. Адабиёт. Таълим. (СамДЧТИ). 2013. №4 (49) –Б. 35-37. (10.00.00; №10)
16. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Даражаланиш ҳодисаси ва градуаллик.// БухДУ илмий ахбороти. 2013. №4 (52). –Б. 37-42. (10.00.00; №1)

17. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Ўзбек ва инглиз тилларида олмошлар градуонимияси.// ЎзМУ хабарлари. 2014. №1. –Б. 340-344. (10.00.00; №15)
18. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. On Lexical Graduonumy. //Вестник Тамбовского университета Серия. Гуманитарные науки. Раздел «Филология» 2011. Выпуск 12 (104). (10.00.00; №14. 01.07.2011).
19. Джумабаева Ж.Ш. Синтактик стилистикада даражаланиш.//Илм сарчашмалари. (УрганчДУ), 2015. №4. –Б. 38-41. (10.00.00; №3)